

Full breastfeeding protection against common enteric bacteria and viruses: Results from the MAL-ED cohort study

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Conflicts of Interest

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Running title

Full breastfeeding lowers risk of enteropathogens

Data availability

Data described in the manuscript will be made available upon request pending application and approval at <http://clinepidb.org>

Abbreviations

BGD	Dhaka, Bangladesh
BRF	Fortaleza, Brazil
EAEC	entero-aggregative <i>Escherichia coli</i>
EIEC	entero-invasive <i>Escherichia coli</i>
ETEC	enterotoxigenic <i>Escherichia coli</i>
INV	Vellore, India
MAL-ED	The Etiology, Risk Factors, and Interactions of Enteric Infections and Malnutrition and the Consequences for Child Health and Development
NEB	Bhaktapur, Nepal
PKN	Naushehro Feroze, Pakistan
PEL	Loreto, Peru
SAV	Venda, South Africa
SES	socio-economic status
tEPEC	typical enteropathogenic <i>Escherichia coli</i>
TZH	Haydom, Tanzania
WAZ	weight-for-age z-score

1 **Abstract**

2 **Background:** Breastfeeding is known to reduce risk of enteropathogen infections, but
3 protection from specific enteropathogens is not well characterized.

4 **Objective:** To estimate the association between full breastfeeding (days fed breast milk
5 exclusively or with non-nutritive liquids) and enteropathogen detection.

6 **Design:** 2,145 newborns were enrolled in eight sites, of whom 1,712 had breastfeeding and
7 key enteropathogen data through 6 months. We focused on eleven enteropathogens:
8 adenovirus 40/41, norovirus, sapovirus, astrovirus, and rotavirus, enterotoxigenic *Escherichia*
9 *coli* (ETEC), *Campylobacter spp*, and typical enteropathogenic *E. coli* as well as entero-
10 aggregative *E. coli*, *Shigella* and *Cryptosporidium*. Logistic regression was used to estimate
11 the risk of enteropathogen detection in stools and survival analysis to estimate the timing of
12 first detection of an enteropathogen.

13 **Results:** Infants with 10% more days of full breastfeeding within the preceding 30 days of a
14 stool sample were less likely to have the three *E. Coli* and *Campylobacter spp* detected in
15 their stool (mean odds 0.92-0.99) but equally likely (0.99-1.02) to have the viral pathogens
16 detected in their stool. A 10% longer period of full breastfeeding from birth was associated
17 with later first detection of the three *E. Coli*, *Campylobacter*, adenovirus, astrovirus, and
18 rotavirus (mean hazard ratios of 0.52-0.75). The hazards declined and point estimates were
19 not statistically significant at 3 months.

20 **Conclusions:** In this large multi-center cohort study, full breastfeeding was associated with
21 lower likelihood of detecting four important enteric pathogens in the first six months of life.
22 These results also show that full breastfeeding is related to delays in the first detection of
23 some bacterial and viral pathogens in the stool. As several of these pathogens are risk factors
24 for poor growth during childhood, this work underscores the importance of exclusive or full
25 breastfeeding during the first six months of life to optimize early health.

26

27 **Keywords**

28 Breastfeeding; enteropathogens; low- and middle-income countries

29

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30 **Introduction**

31 Given the known health advantages of breastfeeding to an infant (1), exclusive breastfeeding
32 is recommended to six months of age with continued breastfeeding to 24 months or longer.

33 Breast milk is a complete diet for infants zero to six months, containing all nutrients an infant
34 requires for healthy growth and development. However, exclusive breastfeeding often ends
35 months earlier than recommended (1,2) with the provision of other milks, including formula
36 and/or solid or semi-solid food. Even when other caloric sources are not introduced,
37 exclusive breastfeeding can be episodic with other liquids (such as water and clear non-
38 nutritive liquids) given to the infant – a practice named predominant breastfeeding (3). Full
39 breastfeeding includes both exclusive and predominant breastfeeding (4) and is known to
40 confer some protection against common childhood illnesses including diarrhea (5–8).

41
42 In addition to containing nutrients, breast milk contains multiple bioactive components which
43 can support the immunity of infants (9). For example, human milk oligosaccharides (10,11)
44 inhibit pathogenic bacteria from attaching to the gut mucosal lining (12–14) and promote gut
45 integrity (15). Additionally, breast milk and individual breast milk components alter the
46 microbiome (16), reduce fecal bacterial diversity (17,18) and also affect gut function (19,20).

47
48 Breastfeeding is associated with reduced diarrheal and respiratory illness, but only a few
49 studies have examined the risk of infection with individual etiologic agents. For example,
50 studies have shown shorter duration or reduced severity of symptoms due to pathogen-
51 specific antibodies in breast milk (10), but not necessarily reduced likelihood of infection
52 (21,22). That said, one study of rotavirus found that severe diarrheal symptoms were delayed
53 (to the second year of life) by full breastfeeding in a setting with high rates of exposure (23).

54

55 Using data from The Etiology, Risk Factors, and Interactions of Enteric Infections and
56 Malnutrition and the Consequences for Child Health and Development (MAL-ED) study
57 (24), we examine whether the duration of full breastfeeding (breast milk inclusive of
58 consumption of non-nutritive liquids) is associated with lower risk of pathogen detection in
59 stool, and secondarily, whether full breastfeeding is associated with delays in the timing of
60 first detecting specific enteropathogens.

61

62 **Methods**

63 *Study*

64 The primary goal of the MAL-ED study was to describe relationships among enteric
65 infections, diet, gut function, and the growth and development of infants and a detailed
66 description (24) and primary results are described elsewhere (25–27). Briefly: infants were
67 enrolled at eight sites in low- and middle-income settings and followed to 24 months of age.
68 Inclusion criteria were enrolment within 17 days of birth (median 7 days, interquartile range
69 4 to 12), born from a singleton pregnancy to a mother at least 16 years of age, birth weight or
70 enrolment weight > 1500 g and no major morbidities, and with a family planning to stay in
71 the community for at least 6 months. Each site chose a target for enrolment with the aim to
72 have data on approximately 200 children per site at 24 months. Enrolment was staggered over
73 two years.² The analyses presented here were restricted to the period from birth to six
74 months, covering the recommended period of exclusive breastfeeding.

75

76 *Pathogens*

77 Households were visited twice weekly to inquire about illness symptoms since the prior visit
78 (28). Stools were collected when mothers reported diarrhea and also collected monthly when
79 children were considered free of diarrhea (separated from symptoms by at least two days)

80 (28). The original study protocol utilized standard techniques to identify enteropathogens in
81 stools, but then quantitative PCR using custom-designed TaqMan Array Cards (Thermo
82 Fisher, Carlsbad, CA, USA) were used to re-analyze the stool samples for the presence of 29
83 enteropathogens (29–31). Here, we focus on the pathogens that accounted for the majority of
84 attributable diarrhea in the first year of life (29): adenovirus 40/41, norovirus, sapovirus,
85 astrovirus, rotavirus, enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (EPEC), *Campylobacter spp* (pan-
86 genus), typical enteropathogenic *E. coli* (tEPEC), *Shigella* and *Cryptosporidium*. We
87 additionally considered entero-aggregative *E. coli* (EAEC) as it was both frequently detected
88 and associated with growth deficits (26). Three countries (Brazil, Peru, and South Africa) had
89 national rotavirus vaccinations at the time of data collection and were excluded from models
90 of rotavirus because vaccination (at approximately two and four months of age) alters the
91 likelihood of infection and/or detection and thereby any association with breastfeeding.
92 Following Rogawski-McQuade *et al.* (32), pathogen presence was defined as a quantitative
93 PCR (qPCR) cycle threshold of <35. Co-infections were also identified when more than one
94 pathogen was detected in a stool sample.

95

96 *Breastfeeding*

97 An interview at enrolment asked for specific details about the timing of breastfeeding
98 initiation, whether or not colostrum was given, and pre-lacteal feeding (33). During the twice
99 weekly surveillance visits, mothers were asked if they had breastfed the child on the previous
100 day and whether or not other liquids or foods had been given and what foods or liquids they
101 were. Infants who were fully breastfed were identified based on these reports. For analysis,
102 we considered the proportion of visits that a child was fully breastfed in two ways. First, to
103 determine whether full breastfeeding was associated with lower likelihood of pathogen
104 detection in stool, we focused on the 30-day period prior to each stool sample collection. We

105 also continued to disaggregated time from the stool collection back to the child's enrolment
106 in 30-day periods to evaluate period-specific associations with full breastfeeding. Second, to
107 determine whether full breastfeeding was associated with delays in the detection of
108 pathogens, we considered time since birth that a child was fully breastfed (exclusive of pre-
109 lacteal feeding). Full breastfeeding as an exposure variable was described either as the
110 proportion of visits between birth and when a given stool was collected or the proportion of
111 time from birth to the age when a pathogen was first detected. In both cases, the proportion of
112 time was multiplied by 10 to give a *per* 10%-time interpretation to coefficients.

113

114 *Covariates*

115 At enrolment, and then monthly, anthropometric assessments (weight, length) were
116 performed by trained workers using standardized protocols (34). Building on risk factors
117 associated with specific pathogens (35–39), we controlled for child sex and weight-for-age
118 (WAZ) at enrolment, the latter evaluated here as a continuous z-score following the WHO
119 growth standards (40). Some pathogen detections were also associated with aspects of lower
120 household socio-economic status (SES) (35,37,41), which was evaluated by questionnaire
121 twice yearly. The SES metric is described in detail elsewhere (42), but briefly was defined
122 using an index (with a range of 0, low SES to 1, high SES) that included access to improved
123 water and sanitation, maternal education, average monthly household income and a range of
124 assets or household attributes (e.g., household crowding). For the purposes of these analyses,
125 the mean SES index across all sampling points was multiplied by 10 to examine a *per* 10%
126 change in socio-economic status. In sensitivity analyses, the raw components of the metric
127 were also examined to determine whether they had greater explanatory power than the
128 combined construct.

129

130 *Ethics*

131 The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Field workers
132 explained the study protocol and obtained written informed consent from a parent or guardian
133 for the children enrolled in the original study. The study was approved by the following
134 institutional review boards which correspond to each site and to collaborating institutions:
135 Institutional Review Board for Health Sciences Research, University of Virginia,
136 Charlottesville, Virginia, USA; the Committee for Ethics in Research, Universidade Federal
137 do Ceara; National Ethical Research Committee, Health Ministry, Council of National Health
138 in Brasília and Fortaleza – Brazil (Brazil site); Institutional Review Board, Johns Hopkins
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140 Committee; Health Ministry, in Loreto – Peru (Peru site); Health, Safety and Research Ethics
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142 Provincial Government, in Venda, South Africa (South Africa site); Medical Research
143 Coordinating Committee, National Institute for Medical Research; Chief Medical Officer,
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148 Medical Research (India site); Institutional Review Board, Institute of Medicine, Tribhuvan
149 University; Ethical Review Board, Nepal Health Research Council; Institutional Review
150 Board, Walter Reed Army Institute of Research in Bhaktapur – Nepal (Nepal site).

151

152 *Statistical Analysis*

153 Site-specific descriptive characteristics of the study sample at enrolment were calculated, as
154 well as site- and pathogen-specific distributions of child age at first detection. The proportion

155 of visits at which full breastfeeding was reported was also calculated by site. Separate
156 modelling approaches were used to address the two questions.

157

158 First, we hypothesized that full breastfeeding would be associated with a lower likelihood of
159 pathogen detection in stools. To test this, a Bayesian multivariable logistic regression model
160 was constructed for each pathogen, with the presence or absence of the pathogen in stool as
161 the outcome. The proportion of visits with a report of full breastfeeding during the current
162 month was the primary exposure variable. Also included were variables for the proportion of
163 full breastfeeding during multiple prior 30-day periods (up to 120 days). Characterized in this
164 way, we capture influences of current full breastfeeding and a history of earlier full
165 breastfeeding. Covariates included infant sex, WAZ at enrolment, the household SES and the
166 count of other pathogens detected in the same stool. Infant age (months) at stool collection
167 was included in the model. Models were further adjusted for site and individual using random
168 effects to account for repeated measurements (an error term to account for the correlation
169 between measurements from the same individual).

170

171 Second, we conducted a survival analysis to test the hypothesis that full breastfeeding would
172 be associated with a delay in the time to first detection of a given pathogen. In this model, the
173 proportion of time fully breastfed (proportion of visits from enrolment to any given stool
174 sample) was treated as a time-varying variable (assuming a log-transformation of age) to
175 account for potential changes with infant age in the association of full breastfeeding with first
176 detection. Site was included as a frailty term, equivalent to a random effect in a linear
177 regression to account for clustering in the repeated observations of each site, and covariates
178 included sex, enrolment WAZ, SES and the number of coincident enteropathogens.

179 All analyses were conducted in R 4.1.0 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna,
180 Austria)

181

182 **Results**

183 From the 2,145 infants enrolled, 1,968 were followed to at least six months, of whom 1,712
184 (87%) were included in these analyses (**Supplementary Figure 1**). Mean infant WAZ at
185 enrolment varied across sites from -1.39 in PKN to -0.13 in TZH (**Table 1**). Although all
186 infants in the analytic sample were initially breastfed, for most, breastfeeding was not
187 initiated within 1 hour of birth. The provision of pre-lacteal feeding varied greatly across
188 sites, from 2.5% in SAV to 63% in PKN. Eighty-five percent (1,313) had the expected
189 number of twice-weekly visits through 180 days (**Supplementary Figure 2**). Overall, the
190 proportion of visits in the first 6 months at which full breastfeeding was reported varied from
191 26.0% in SAV to 94.0% in BGD (**Table 1**); the proportion of visits with full breastfeeding
192 was high during the first two months except in PKN, and declined over the time period
193 (**Figure 1**).

194

195 By six months old, infants in these settings experienced a mean prevalence of 14.1 days of
196 diarrhea per child-year (varying by site from 0.6 in BRF to 50.7 in PKN). Pathogens were
197 frequently isolated from both the monthly non-diarrheal and the diarrheal stools: the most
198 frequently identified pathogens were EAEC and *Campylobacter spp.* with 86% and 48% of
199 infants in the study experiencing these respective pathogens at least once in the first six
200 months of life. The timing of first pathogen detection varied across sites (**Figure 2 and Table**
201 **2**) as did the proportion of first detections from a diarrheal as opposed to a monthly
202 surveillance stool. The first detection of astrovirus and ETEC tended to occur around three
203 months of age and the other pathogens tended to temporally cluster around four months of

204 age (**Table 2**). However, the 25th percentile for first detection of many pathogens was about
205 60 days (the median across all pathogens, 63 days) indicating that many infants were exposed
206 and infected in the first few months of life. *Shigella* and *Cryptosporidium* had distinctly
207 different profiles to the other pathogens analysed here and were rarely detected in some sites
208 during the first six months of life (e.g. two detections of *Cryptosporidium* in BRF and just
209 four in NEB). Although variable by pathogen and by site, the majority of first detections of
210 pathogens were from a surveillance as opposed to a diarrheal stool (Table 2).

211

212 The results of the logistic regression evaluating the association between full breastfeeding
213 and the odds of detecting an enteropathogen are shown in **Figure 3**. Each 10% more visits
214 with reported full breastfeeding in the 30 days prior to a stool sample collection was
215 associated with significantly lower odds of detecting *Campylobacter* (0.94, 95% CI: 0.93,
216 0.97), EAEC, (0.95, 95% CI: 0.93, 0.96), ETEC (0.94, 95% CI: 0.92, 0.95), and tEPEC (0.92,
217 95% CI: 0.90, 0.93) in a stool. No difference in odds was found for *Shigella*,
218 *Cryptosporidium* and or any of the five viral pathogens (odds of 0.99 to 1.02). Prior (more
219 historic) full breastfeeding had inconsistent associations with the odds of pathogen detection,
220 and this varied by site (**Supplementary Figure 3**).

221

222 In the survival model, full breastfeeding was associated with longer time to first infections
223 (**Figure 4** and coefficients in **Supplementary Figure 4** and by site in **Supplementary**
224 **Figure 5**). Here, the proportion of visits with full breastfeeding from enrolment to the first
225 detection of each pathogen before six months of age was evaluated, and for every 10% of
226 time a caregiver reported full breastfeeding, the hazard ratio (HR) of first detecting most
227 pathogens was reduced (**Figure 4**). The trend was for the main effect of full breastfeeding to
228 be similarly protective of the viruses and bacteria (with the exception of *Shigella*, norovirus

229 and *Cryptosporidium*, two of which as noted were rare at these ages in these infants and
230 consequently had wide confidence intervals) with the mean hazard ratios at birth of 0.52
231 (95% CI: 0.37, 0.73) for *Campylobacter*, 0.54 (95% CI: 0.33, 0.87) for tEPEC, 0.60 (95% CI:
232 0.45, 0.80) for ETEC, 0.75 (95% CI: 0.61, 0.91) for EAEC, 0.55 (95% CI: 0.33, 0.91) for
233 rotavirus, 0.55 (95% CI: 0.36, 0.85) for sapovirus, 0.66 (95% CI: 0.49, 0.89) for adenovirus,
234 and 0.67 (95% CI: 0.47, 0.94) for astrovirus. The protection attributed to full breastfeeding
235 diminished over time during the first six months of life. On average, by three months old, the
236 marginal protection from full breastfeeding was predicted to have reduced substantially,
237 ranged from 0.89 to 1.0 and not statistically significant.. The main effect and interaction with
238 time were $p \leq 0.01$ for all pathogens except adenovirus (main effect, $p=0.02$; interaction,
239 $p=0.04$), norovirus ($p=0.22$; $p=0.32$), *Cryptosporidium* ($p=0.15$; $p=0.22$) and *Shigella*
240 ($p=0.52$; $p=0.48$).

241

242 We included covariates in each of these models depicting variation in initial breastfeeding
243 practices. As shown, the timing of breastfeeding initiation and whether or not colostrum was
244 given were inconsistently associated with pathogen detections and had very wide confidence
245 intervals (Figures 3 and Supplementary Figure 4). A higher SES was generally protective
246 against bacterial detection and to a lesser extent, against viral pathogens (Figures 3 and
247 Supplementary Figure 4), whereas female sex was protective of viral detection in some
248 models. Coinfections in the stool samples were common; each non-diarrheal stool had a
249 median of 1 enteropathogens detected (IQR 0 to 2) and diarrheal samples had 2
250 enteropathogens (IQR 1 to 3). Additional enteropathogen detections within the same stool
251 were highly predictive of detection for each of the pathogens.

252

253 **Discussion**

254 Exclusive breastfeeding of infants for the first six months of life is recommended globally
255 both as a complete source of nutrition for infants and because of the wide-ranging health
256 benefits, including a reduced likelihood of enteric disease. Although almost all infants in this
257 study were breastfed, many caregivers reported full breastfeeding, meaning they reported
258 days of exclusive breastfeeding, and on some days reported giving water and/or non-nutritive
259 liquids. Previously we have shown that during an infant's first six months many caregivers
260 begin feeding other milks and/or solids (3). Although we have shown that a pattern of more
261 than 50% days of exclusive breastfeeding is associated with lower risk of diarrheal illness
262 during the period of recommended exclusive breastfeeding (8), here we focus on the more
263 common feeding pattern of full breastfeeding and evaluate exposure to specific bacterial and
264 viral pathogens. We present evidence that even in settings with high rates of enteropathogen
265 exposure, a longer duration of full breastfeeding is associated with lower odds of detection of
266 some bacterial enteropathogens and a longer time to first infection of some bacterial and viral
267 pathogens.

268

269 Exclusive breastfeeding may protect an infant from pathogens because of reduced oral
270 exposure, and to the extent that water or other non-nutritive liquids are treated, the same may
271 be true when there are intermittent days of full breastfeeding. Human milk has multiple
272 constituents which are known to protect infants from infection and disease, including
273 secretory IgA (sIgA) antibodies, its own microbiota, human milk oligosaccharides, and other
274 antimicrobial factors (e.g. lactoferrin, alpha-lactalbumin, beta-defensins), glycoproteins, and
275 extracellular vesicles (43–45). Human milk also contains viruses which are bacteriophages
276 (46). As recently reviewed by Nadimpalli *et al.*, (43), there is evidence that full breastfeeding
277 is protective of acquisition and in some cases of first acquisition of specific enteropathogens.
278 Our findings add to that literature by demonstrating consistent negative associations between

279 the extent of full breastfeeding and detection of key bacterial pathogens that are principal
280 causes of diarrhea in these infants and worldwide. We extend those findings by showing that
281 full breastfeeding duration is associated with later first acquisition of bacterial and viral
282 pathogens.

283

284 The timing of infections, and hence the rate of exposure, varied by site as might be expected,
285 and the median age at which infants started to encounter diarrheagenic pathogens was three
286 months. Many epidemiological factors contributed to this, several of which have been
287 previously examined in this cohort for some of these pathogens and include socio-economic
288 status and maternal education, birth weight and the environment (35–39). Nevertheless, even
289 accounting for inter-site variability in exposures, including breastfeeding patterns, there are
290 consistent results for some pathogens.

291

292 We found evidence that full breastfeeding (over the past 30 days) was protective against
293 detecting four of the bacterial pathogens examined, *Campylobacter*, ETEC, tEPEC and
294 EAEC. However, current breastfeeding represents the most recent manifestation of a pattern
295 of feeding, and older infants with a higher proportion of visits with reported full
296 breastfeeding have a longer history of full breastfeeding. Thus, our results indicate that the
297 longer the duration of full breastfeeding, the longer there is a lower risk of detecting
298 pathogenic bacteria even though as shown (Figure 4) the protection diminishes over time
299 during the first six months of life. There is long-standing evidence that human milk can
300 contain specific sIgA antibodies against *Campylobacter* (10) and that lactoferrin inhibits the
301 proliferation of *E. coli* in the gut (47). In contrast, recent full breastfeeding did not show
302 protective effect against viral detections. One possible reason is that viral pathogens convey a

303 stronger immune response than many of the bacterial pathogens and this reduces the
304 likelihood of repeated infections (32).

305

306 In our second model, delay in first detection of adenovirus, sapovirus, astrovirus and
307 rotavirus were associated with longer duration of full breastfeeding (expressed as % of days
308 from enrolment to stool collection). This is consistent with a study of rotavirus that reported a
309 delay in the rotavirus-associated diarrhea for exclusively breastfed infants in the first six
310 months of life (23). Here, rotavirus detections were confounded by vaccination, therefore, the
311 three sites with routine vaccination were excluded from the analyses. Liu *et al.* (48)
312 speculated that protection against sapovirus might follow that of norovirus, for which
313 antibodies have been detected in breast milk (49). Although the degree of full breastfeeding
314 was not significantly associated with time to first detection of sapovirus or norovirus in these
315 results, the mean effect was still protective as is consistent with other research (50).

316

317 This study benefitted from consistent and rigorous quality control to produce comparable
318 data across diverse populations. This included both the collection of breastfeeding practices
319 through twice weekly surveillance, as well as collection of stools during diarrhea and on non-
320 diarrhea days. The identification of pathogens from these stools using PCR techniques
321 allowed us to evaluate detection of specific pathogens, while considering other pathogens,
322 and to focus on those with most demonstrated relevance for diarrheal morbidity and growth
323 faltering across the sites. However, mechanistic understanding of the association between
324 breastfeeding and enteropathogen detections was not possible because collection of human
325 milk samples was not part of the study protocol.

326

327 This study provides empirical evidence that full breastfeeding reduces the likelihood of
328 acquiring four diarrheagenic bacterial enteropathogens in infants' stools, but not viruses. Full
329 breastfeeding also delayed the first detection of some pathogens, including both viruses and
330 bacteria. These results underscore the importance of promoting full breastfeeding in
331 protecting infants in settings of high rates of exposure to enteropathogens from both clinical
332 (diarrhea) and sub-clinical (no diarrhea) infections both of which have been shown to have
333 detrimental associations with growth and development (26,27).

334

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345 **Author contributions**

346 BJJM, SAR, LEMK and LEC designed the research, contributed to the analysis and
347 interpretation of results, and wrote the manuscript. BJJM and SAR SAR performed the
348 statistical analysis. ETRM supported the qPCR data analysis, and interpretation. ERH and
349 ETRM GK, MNK, ERH and ETRM provided valuable interpretation. GK, AAML, EM,
350 MNK, PB, SS, ZB, and TA led site data acquisition, the design of the original protocol, and

351 data interpretation. All authors reviewed and approved the manuscript. A full listing of all
352 MAL-ED Network Investigators is provided in the supplemental material.

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Table 1: Selected characteristics of the analytic population

	BGD ¹	INV	NEB	PKN	BRF	PEL	SAV	TZH
N	210	227	226	246	164	194	236	209
Visits with full breastfeeding ² (%)	94 [73, 100]	67 [48, 81]	63 [36, 83]	30 [9, 65]	56 [29, 88]	92 [77, 100]	26 [12, 43]	31 [18, 47]
Male (n (%))	102 (48.6)	122 (53.7)	105 (46.5)	126 (51.2)	75 (45.7)	89 (45.9)	116 (49.2)	104 (49.8)
WAZ enrolment (mean (SD))	-1.26 (0.94)	-1.30 (1.04)	-0.92 (0.97)	-1.39 (1.05)	-0.17 (1.05)	-0.62 (0.91)	-0.37 (0.94)	-0.13 (0.94)
Received colostrum (n (%))	206 (98.1)	204 (89.9)	219 (96.9)	204 (82.9)	161 (98.2)	188 (96.9)	228 (96.6)	194 (92.8)
BF initiated >1h (n (%))	82 (39.2)	93 (41.0)	133 (58.8)	228 (93.1)	88 (53.7)	51 (26.3)	79 (38.3)	34 (16.3)
Prelacteal feeding (n (%))	29 (13.8)	26 (11.5)	41 (18.1)	155 (63.0)	12 (7.3)	15 (7.7)	6 (2.5)	8 (3.8)
SES ³ (median [IQR])	0.53 [0.45, 0.63]	0.48 [0.36, 0.57]	0.70 [0.61, 0.80]	0.49 [0.35, 0.62]	0.84 [0.79, 0.90]	0.54 [0.45, 0.62]	0.79 [0.71, 0.85]	0.21 [0.14, 0.29]

¹Abbreviations used: BGD, Dhaka, Bangladesh; INV, Vellore, India; NEB, Bhaktapur, Nepal; PKN, Naushehro Feroze, Pakistan; BRF, Fortaleza, Brazil; PEL, Loreto, Peru; SAV, Venda, South Africa; TZH, Haydom, Tanzania; BF, breastfeeding; SES, socioeconomic status.²Over the period from enrolment to 180 days. ³SES was measured using an in-sample index that included access to improved water and sanitation, maternal education, average monthly household income and a range of assets (that include household crowding).

Table 2: Median (inter-quartile range) age (in days) when selected enteropathogens were first detected during the first six months of life and the total number (N) of children with at least one positive test for each pathogen of which the percent of those first detections that came from diarrheal stools. Rotavirus is not shown for the three sites with national vaccination.

Pathogen		BGD ¹	INV	NEB	PKN	BRF	PEL	SAV	TZH
	N	210	227	226	246	164	194	236	209
Adenovirus	median (IQR)	92 (62, 143)	94 (62, 123)	120 (90, 151)	119 (60, 150)	121 (93, 127)	91 (60, 128)	91 (60, 122)	121 (88, 152)
	N (% diarrhea)	146 (36.3)	128 (8.6)	77 (16.9)	146 (38.4)	25 (8)	137 (24.8)	71 (0)	103 (5.8)
Norovirus	median (IQR)	121 (90, 150)	120 (90, 150)	123 (96, 153)	99 (58, 138)	124 (92, 150)	122 (90, 152)	121 (89, 138)	120 (89, 151)
	N (% diarrhea)	86 (22.1)	85 (12.9)	55 (25.5)	152 (38.8)	18 (0)	73 (26)	63 (3.2)	118 (5.1)
Sapovirus	median (IQR)	112 (60, 150)	121 (90, 152)	151 (100, 154)	113 (61, 152)	65 (60, 86)	116 (90, 151)	94 (59, 128)	150 (92, 156)
	N (% diarrhea)	84 (34.5)	67 (20.9)	23 (21.7)	92 (40.2)	6 (0)	53 (26.4)	46 (2.2)	48 (12.5)
Astrovirus	median (IQR)	93 (76, 123)	92 (69, 124)	110 (92, 144)	89 (58, 122)	106 (83, 154)	91 (62, 143)	120 (88, 138)	120 (61, 150)
	N (% diarrhea)	130 (26.2)	90 (23.3)	14 (21.4)	135 (54.1)	8 (0)	113 (21.2)	31 (3.2)	63 (6.3)
Rotavirus	median (IQR)	92 (67, 145)	90 (58, 119)	127 (110, 147)	96 (62, 150)	--	--	--	122 (88, 152)
	N (% diarrhea)	120 (55.8)	90 (11.1)	24 (45.8)	54 (53.7)				44 (18.2)
ETEC	median (IQR)	91 (59, 123)	103 (62, 150)	148 (111, 154)	91 (58, 124)	93 (64, 121)	92 (58, 150)	94 (62, 124)	91 (61, 123)
	N (% diarrhea)	156 (29.5)	117 (17.9)	82 (20.7)	127 (34.6)	24 (8.3)	113 (19.5)	40 (5)	157 (5.7)
<i>Campylobacter</i> spp	median (IQR)	110 (70, 149)	91 (61, 137)	122 (76, 152)	100 (61, 151)	122 (93, 151)	92 (60, 148)	93 (60, 125)	100 (88, 127)
	N (% diarrhea)	110 (21.8)	101 (7.9)	70 (22.9)	120 (47.5)	20 (5)	70 (35.7)	69 (2.9)	126 (4.8)
tEPEC	median (IQR)	124 (90, 153)	100 (60, 151)	138 (120, 151)	106 (64, 150)	122 (92, 152)	93 (60, 155)	92 (62, 135)	124 (92, 154)
	N (% diarrhea)	74 (23)	82 (12.2)	20 (35)	109 (50.5)	9 (0)	45 (33.3)	21 (14.3)	96 (4.2)
EAEC	median (IQR)	91 (62, 122)	61 (32, 93)	92 (59, 150)	59 (31, 89)	97 (62, 126)	61 (31, 104)	90 (60, 122)	65 (58, 92)
	N (% diarrhea)	175 (12)	213 (7)	137 (12.4)	221 (33)	75 (4)	166 (18.1)	146 (2.1)	204 (7.8)
<i>Shigella</i> /EIEC	median (IQR)	98 (89, 152)	94 (60, 150)	150 (115, 160)	111 (79, 151)	96 (92, 136)	98 (60, 153)	62 (60, 109)	91 (70, 141)
	N (% diarrhea)	16 (31.2)	24 (8.3)	10 (60)	20 (55)	7 (14.3)	12 (25)	11 (0)	31 (9.7)
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	median (IQR)	95 (68, 127)	122 (82, 140)	107 (84, 131)	146 (121, 153)	107 (100, 114)	91 (62, 136)	123 (121, 151)	93 (60, 153)
	N (% diarrhea)	17 (5.9)	12 (25)	4 (50)	30 (60)	2 (0)	22 (22.7)	16 (0)	23 (8.7)

¹Abbreviations used: BGD, Dhaka, Bangladesh; INV, Vellore, India; NEB, Bhaktapur, Nepal; PKN, Naushehro Feroze, Pakistan; BRF, Fortaleza, Brazil; PEL, Loreto, Peru; SAV, Venda, South Africa; TZH, Haydom, Tanzania; ETEC, enterotoxigenic *E. coli*; tEPEC, typical enteropathogenic *E. coli*; EAEC, entero-aggregative *E. coli*; EIEC, entero-invasive *E. coli*.

Figures

Figure 1: Proportion of visits recording full breastfeeding for infants in each of the first six months of life by site (n=1712 children). BGD: Bangladesh, Dhaka; INV: India, Vellore; NEB: Nepal, Bhaktapur; BRF: Brazil, Fortaleza; PEL: Peru, Loreto; SAV: South Africa, Venda; TZH: Tanzania, Haydom.

Figure 2: Kaplan-Meier plots of the time until selected enteropathogens were first detected at each of the eight MAL-ED sites (n = 1712 children). BGD: Bangladesh, Dhaka; INV: India, Vellore; NEB: Nepal, Bhaktapur; BRF: Brazil, Fortaleza; PEL: Peru, Loreto; SAV: South Africa, Venda; TZH: Tanzania, Haydom.

Figure 3: The odds ratio (mean and 95% credibility interval) of detecting enteropathogens in stools as a function of the proportion of visits reporting full breastfeeding (BF) in 30-day periods preceding stool collection. Showing viral (left) and bacterial (right) pathogens. SES, socio-economic index (per 10% increase, an index including water, sanitation, education and wealth); WAZ, weight-for-age assessed at enrolment; full BF proportion, the proportion of visits reporting full breastfeeding from enrolment to each stool sample is considered as both a main effect and time varying term (multiplied by the $\log(\text{age})$); BF initiated, whether or not breastfeeding was initiated within the first hour after birth; other pathogens, a count of pathogen detected in the stool (excluding the pathogen of the response variable). Logistic regression models also controlled for site as a random effect. n = 1712 children except for the rotavirus model that excludes the three sites with routine vaccination (BRF, PEL, SAV), n = 1118. The intercept and age coefficients are not shown.

Figure 4: The marginal hazard ratios for the first detection of enteropathogens as a function of the proportion of time from birth to stool sampling when the child received full breastfeeding. The survival models also adjusted for socio-economic status (including water, sanitation, education and wealth), weight-for-age assessed at enrolment, breastfeeding initiation, sex and the count of coincident enteropathogens. Full breastfeeding was included as both a main effect and time varying term (multiplied by the $\log(\text{age})$). Models also controlled for site using a frailty term. n = 1712 children except for the rotavirus model that excludes the three sites with routine vaccination (BRF, PEL, SAV), n = 1118.

Viruses

Bacteria

ONLINE SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

**Full breastfeeding protection against common enteric bacteria and viruses:
Results from the MAL-ED cohort study**

McCormick, BJJ

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	BGD	INV	NEB	PKN	BRF	PEL	SAV	TZH	TOTAL
Enrolled	265	251	240	277	233	303	314	262	2145
Dropped out <180 d	23	15	4	12	24	33	53	13	177
No pathogen data <6 mo	32	9	10	19	45	76	24	40	255
Analytic sample	210	227	226	246	164	194	236*	209	1713

Supplemental Figure 1: Cohort profile. * One child from SAV was missing socio-economic data and was removed.

Supplemental Figure 2: Proportion of twice-weekly visits met.

Supplemental Figure 3: The odds of detecting pathogens in stools as a function of the proportion of full breastfeeding (BF) in each 30-day period preceding the stool collection. Showing the coefficients for the lagged full BF terms by site (colored dots) and overall (black triangles). Models were adjusted for site and age, SES, coincidence enteropathogens and child sex. Sites: BGD, Dhaka, Bangladesh; INV, Vellore, India; NEB, Bhaktapur, Nepal; BRF, Fortaleza, Brazil; PEL, Loreto, Peru; SAV, Venda, South Africa; TZH, Haydom, Tanzania. The rotavirus model excludes the three sites with vaccine (BRF, PEL, SAV).

Supplemental Figure 4: Hazard ratios of risk factors derived from survival models for time to first detection of specific pathogens. Showing viral (left) and bacterial (right) pathogens. SES, socio-economic index (per 10% increase); WAZ, weight-for-age assessed at enrolment; full BF proportion, the proportion of visits reporting full breastfeeding from enrolment to each stool sample is considered as both a main effect and time varying term (multiplied by the log(age)); BF initiated, whether or not breastfeeding was initiated within the first hour after birth. Models also controlled for site as a random effect. The rotavirus model excludes the three sites with vaccine (BRF, PEL, SAV). The intercept is not shown.

Supplemental Figure 5: Hazard ratios of risk factors derived from survival models for the most diarrheagenic childhood enteropathogens. SES, socio-economic index (per 10% increase); WAZ, weight-for-age assessed at enrollment; full BF proportion, the proportion of time from birth to each stool sample when the child was fully breastfed as a main effect and, where applicable, as a time varying term (multiplied by the log(age)). Models also controlled for site as a random effect. Sites: BGD, Dhaka, Bangladesh; INV, Vellore, India; NEB, Bhaktapur, Nepal; BRF, Fortaleza, Brazil; PEL, Loreto, Peru; SAV, Venda, South Africa; TZH, Haydom, Tanzania. The rotavirus model excludes the three sites with vaccine (BRF, PEL, SAV).